

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

(To be filled in and uploaded as deliverable in the Portal Grant Management System, at the due date foreseen in the system (and regularly updated).)

⚠️ The template is recommended but not mandatory. If you do not use it, please make however sure that you comply with the research data management requirements under Article 17 of the Grant Agreement.)

PROJECT	
Project number:	[101059015]
Project acronym:	[HaloCell]
Project name:	[Harnessing Halogen Bond in Perovskite Solar Cells]

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	
Date:	[23/07/2024]
Version:	[1]

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

No pre-existing data will be used for this project.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The project will generate data related to the properties (physical and chemical) of the new materials. In all cases, the data will be in machine readable formats: i.e. ".cif" (crystallographic information file), ".csv" (comma-separated value) and ".opj" (origin project) formats. In the case of figures and images ".jpg" and ".png" formats.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Data generation is related to the objectives of the project, more specific to the designed experimental work, and constitutes the information related to the characterization of new chemical compounds and materials, their physical and chemical properties.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The total size of the generated data is estimated to be in the scale of few gigabytes (1-5GBs).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The origin of the generated data is the software programs that operating the different experimental setups and infrastructures (i.e. spectrometers, diffractometers), diagrams and digital images depicting the developed processes.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The generated data is of interest for the broader scientific community, starting from chemistry (i.e. characterization data of new chemical compounds) and physics (i.e. characterization data of materials photophysical properties).and moving to interdisciplinary fields (i.e. crystallographic characterization data).

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Published data will be accompanied by digital object identifiers (DOIs). Crystallographic data of deposited structures will be identified by a discrete persistent identifier (DOI). Data concerning publications will also be accompanied by the DOI of the parent publication.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

To allow discovery of crystallographic data, identification numbers, compound names, chemical details (chemical formula), crystal details (i.e. colour, size) and experimental details (i.e. temperature) will be provided. This metadata produced by the utilized crystallographic software, constituting the timeline of each performed experiment. In the case of publications, author(s) and organizations involved, title, date of publication, acknowledgement of Horizon Europe funding, grant project name, acronym and the persistent identifier (DOI) for the publication, will be provided. For the involved authors the ORCID identifier will be utilized, while CORDIS will be used for the metadata related to project's information and results.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

When applicable, additional keywords will be also provided to increase the possibility of discovery.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Metadata will be deposited to trusted repositories (CCDC, Figshare, arXiv, Web of Science, Scopus, CORDIS) allowing harvesting and indexing.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Crystallographic data will be deposited to the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) database. Other experimental data will be deposited to Figshare.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Appropriate arrangements have been arranged with the "CIF (data) deposition and validation service" of CCDC.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Upon data deposition, each entry receives a unique digital object identifier (DOI) and is connected to the parent publication.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Data used in publications will be openly available. In case of data potentially subjected to intellectual property rights (IPR) and commercial exploitation, will not be made openly available.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as

soon as possible.

Publication of data subjected to IPR may be postponed for a maximum period of 2 years.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Published data will be accessible through web repositories i.e. Figshare and CCDC.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Published data will be available with no restrictions, unless IPR restrictions.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

In the case of open data, no information regarding the identity of the person accessing the data will be required. In case of IPR restrictions, the identity of the person accessing the data will be ascertained via a formal inquiry (i.e. through the “patents and intellectual property management service” of the host institution).

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

The project treats no sensitive data.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Metadata will be openly available using a repository likewise the “Figshare” or “arXiv”, including data access.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

The published data will remain available and findable as long as the repositories are active. The related metadata will be harvested by multiple sources likewise: CCDC, Figshare, arXiv, Web of Science, Scopus, ORCID, Cordis etc.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The access and read of the data will require common commercial software, which will be mentioned if necessary.

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

All produced data and metadata will be in line to common practises of the research community with no barriers between different disciplines. This will include reporting of data acquiring and processing conditions.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

This project will use standard terminology in the fields of chemistry, physics, materials and engineering.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful

previous research)?

The data of this project will not include qualified references.

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Published data will be in the form of commonly used file extensions and will be accompanied by all relative information related to the instrumentation used and the conditions.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Published data will be distributed in line to the FAIR obligations.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Published data will be open to the community.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

All published data will be accompanied by all necessary information regarding their generation.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality assurance includes the following measures: maintenance of the infrastructure; technical description of the utilized infrastructure; reporting the experimental conditions; reporting the condition of the analysed specimen; reporting the methodology; reporting data collection method; reporting the (possible) data treatment (i.e. instrument corrections) and software or hardware used to generate and distribute the datasheet.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

The project is based on the development of new chemical compounds and materials. Within the duration of the project, these outputs will remain in the context of laboratory-scale production.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

New compounds and materials will be produced for covering the needs of the project. All new data are tightly bound to them. In this context, the FAIR data above are including their development, use and re-use. The same will apply in the case of IPR and potential commercialization of the developed compounds and materials.

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Costs related to open-access publications will be considered.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Costs related to open-access publications will be covered by the current grant.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The supervisor and the co-supervisor of the project will be responsible for the data management.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

No costs have been foreseen. The supervisor and the co-supervisor of the project will evaluate the potential value of all data and decide how to manage the data.

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data will be also self-archived and protected to allow data recovery. This project will produce no sensitive data.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Published data will be safely stored in trusted repositories.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethical concerns will emerge from data sharing.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

The project will not deal with personal data.

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No other procedures have been foreseen.